

Time-Pressure (TP) – Instructions

The *italicized* and bold **text** is the instruction and non-italicized text is a speech content.

----- Before 11:55 -----

Setting the laptop for the projection of the application UI's screenshot.

----- 11:55 -----

Routing participants to TP and NTP classes. Apply complete Randomisation to the participants.

Ask every arriving participant:

“Did you sign the consent form and fill in the questionnaire?”

If he/she says, “Yes”, then send to TP or NTP group. Route them to TP and NTP alternatively. Try to achieve a balanced group of TP and NTP participants.

If he/she says, “No” then send either to TP or to NTP - it doesn't matter.

BUT

If he/she shows willingness to participate then hand over the consent form and pre-questionnaire. When they are done with these docs then route to either TP or NTP group following the same alternative and balanced scheme of assignment to TP and NTP groups.

----- 12:20 -----

When all the participants are set

Handing out the

MusicFone Task - overturned

Template-printed sheet - overturned

Stationery (pencils, erasers, sharpeners)

The in-class exercise today is about generating the functional test-cases from the requirement specification document. The special thing about the specification document that you are using today is, it is a proper document from the industry. So, these are the real specifications of a mobile-application. This exercise is like the one you have done recently but there is another thing about it, as mentioned earlier you are going to be the subjects of the research activity while doing this exercise. I am informing you this because please, do not interact with or distract others. If you have a question, just raise your hand and I'll attend that. That said, there is nothing extra or special you need to do just perform this as a regular exercise just like the one you performed earlier.

(If someone asks or complaints about not being the part of the experiment; tell this:

“I would also like to inform you that, those of you, who did not wish to be part of the

research activity, your data will not be used.”)

----- 12:30 -----

Please, take 5 minutes to give the task a quick reading. And if there is anything that you don't understand please, ask.

Please, write your student-ID on the template-sheet.

Now, if you look at the sheet, an example case has already been provided to you. This tests one of the requirements by being very specific to what it wants to test by its description. Then there is a column called input/pre-conditions where you are supposed to write in the input value - the exact value and the preconditions - if you think that along with the particular input value there must be some conditions that must be met to test the particular requirement. Then in the Expected output/post-condition section you have to write the expected output value - the value that you think should appear as a result of what you want to test. If you can recall the lecture on functional testing by Sira - the professor from Spain – she showed you a similar table to be filled in at the end of her last lecture where the column “description” was named as “test-goal”. So, this is similar.

Project the UI - Telling about projected MusicFone UI.

This is the screenshot of the implemented MusicFone Task. This is presented for your help to understand the task and so to come up with the test-cases.

You have ONLY 30 minutes to complete the WHOLE Task.

If someone is done before time then please, let me know by raising your hand.

When someone claims that he/she is finished with the task - handle it this way: Put a timestamp mark on the sheet against the latest test-case he/she has written and tell to continue if he/she wants to, otherwise he waits in the class for the next activity.

----- 12:45 -----

This is an individual task so please, do not talk with each other. If you have to ask something then ask me. You can ask for extra-sheets if you need.

If someone asks for an extra-sheet, make sure that they put their student-ID first.

You may begin now.

Tick, tick, tick...

You have Only 15 minutes left to complete the WHOLE Task.

Tick, tick, tick...

You have Only 10 minutes left now for the Task.

Tick, tick, tick...

You are now left with 5 minutes Only.

If someone asks the time then announce to all the participants.

If someone asks something about the task, just tell him, “Do what you understand from this”.

----- 13:15 or 01:15 pm-----

Time-Over-Call to the participants.

Collect the sheets.

Ask the last person sitting in the corner to start passing his worksheet(s) to the next and so on to the first person.

Now I'll collect your opinion about the task-load. This technique is developed by NASA to assess how the person who performs a task perceives the work-load of the task.

Handing out the bunch of cards and definition-sheet to the participants

The first action you'll perform is called the 15-point comparison of sources-of-load. Each card has two attributes and you have to circle the one, which in your opinion was the most demanding for the task.

Write your student ID on the first card. If you have any questions, please, ask.

Handing out the Magnitude of Load (Ratings) sheets

In this sheet we have all the sources-of-load demands along with the rating-scale of each. The scale is from 0 to 100 in increments of 5, i.e. it runs from low to high and you have to rate the workload-source by marking a tick on the scale. If you have any questions please, ask.

----- 13:30 or 01:30 pm -----

Collection of NASA-TLX Material

And

Make Sure that everyone has put his student-ID on the all materials being returned.